

THE MAIN ASPECTS THAT NEED TO BE CONSIDERED IN THE PROCESS OF VOCAL PERFORMANCE.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6377513>

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Annotation: *This article focuses on the processes encountered in the vocal art and what needs more attention in the performance process. This article answers the questions of what is encountered in the process of vocal performance, in what position to sing, how to breathe, the vocal apparatus and how to use it.*

Keywords: *Vocal, sound, breath, vocal apparatus, performing arts, intonation.*

In the process of working with the student, it is important to study the singing apparatus, to analyze the performance technique. If the talent for the performer is to express the music in a meaningful way by feeling it in the heart then the knowledge is to irrigate this talent with the performance skills of the music science genres their straightforward and metrorhythmic aspects. In the words of musicologist Rajabov he must have mastered the technique of playing the shashmaqom and other large forms of folk music. That is they must master the science of music performance. The interpretation of the performance requires a perfect sound with a beautiful subtle and wide range in the singer. At the same time, it is important to use the available voice wisely.

Performance has long been a unique form based on the different genre characteristics of our musical heritage. Their spiritual influence is divided into 3 groups of performing traditions based on the structural and positive aspects of musical live expression. These are the most developed forms of folklore folk professional and traditions. The performers were successors of the so called traditions and had an impact on the development of the art of music. All the groups mentioned above are interconnected has undergone a process of development in with the breath of time. Performers are the successors of the so-called traditions that have influenced the development of the art music. The process of historical development of performance has laid the foundation for the formation of methods oasis group and individual performance in the local zones within certain groups and on the basis of independent creativity. In local zone performance styles, various aspects that characterize a particular local direction such as the of sheva tradition play an important role as a key factor. It is necessary to give a reliable knowledge of the correct market teacher apprentice from which field. There is practical and theoretical knowledge that a student should know in the

performing arts, whether it is a national or a national direction. For example, when singing what should he pay attention to in what situation should be perform and so on. The larynx plays an important role in the production of sound. Unrestricted free position of the larynx is the most convenient for singing.

When the song is sung, the creative collaboration intensifies and unites in a friendly team. With the help of vocal skills, they have a deep understanding of the meaning of the song and the tone of the music, and learn about life through the content of the work. In order to achieve the above results, it is necessary to develop the following vocal skills and adhere to them when singing as a group. Because it is the vocal skill, the instrument that can achieve a pleasant sound. Vocal skills are divided into 6 types.

Singing status in class; Singing breath; Sound generation; Adjustable; Ensemble; Pronunciation;

The larynx plays an important role in the production of sound. The unrestricted free position of the larynx is the most convenient for singing. In this case the air pushed by the lungs encounters closed vocal cards and vibrations occur in the air. The tormation at variable sound strands is a sound wave but for a person to pronounce a letter or sound the lips need a soft palate of the tongue and the active porticipation of others. The well cordinated work of all the organs of sound formation transforms simple sounds into songs. The nasal cavity also plays an important role. Together with the accessary threads, it participates in the formation of sound. The sounds is louder here. The sonorous timbre is given. The position of the cavity and paranasal sinusess has a certain value for the correct pronunciation of speech sounds and the timbre of the voice. It is their individuality that gives each person a unique timbre.

The pronunciation in singing is different from the pronunciation of speech. As a result of active coordination of articulatory organs (lips, tongue, jaw), ambiguity, squeezing of the vocal apparatus, there are defects in singing. Such children need to be given more attention and encouraged to work with them alone for long periods of time, to speak freely and to sing slowly. It is necessary to learn to breathe correctly and to finish the sentence, to stretch the vowels, to sing the consonant sounds burro, piece by piece. At the same time it is necessary to pay special attention to the shape of the mouth, the movements of the tongue, changes. Most importantly, children should be taught to practice and pronounce the lyrics in accordance with the vocal style.

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